

EXTENDED HIGH ORDER THEORY FOR SANDWICH PANELS AND COMPARISON WITH ELASTICITY

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ABSTRACT

The linear and the non-linear behavior of a curved sandwich panel with a stiff or compliant core when subjected to a pressure load is presented. First, the Extended High Order Sandwich Panel Theory (EHSPAT), which had been formulated up to now for the beam or plate configuration, is extended to the case of a curved panel. Based on the derivation of the displacement field from the equations of elasticity for a zero in-plane rigidity core assumption, the displacement is suggested to have a logarithmic dependence on the radial coordinate (this was also the assumption in the HSAPT theory). Thus, two cases are considered: a logarithmic functional dependence of the assumed displacement field and a polynomial dependence (just as in the plate formulation). In order to assess the merits of each approach, an Elasticity solution is derived for the special case of a simply-supported panel and sinusoidal distributed external pressure. The Elasticity solution is formulated based on the displacement approach and it is in closed form. It is proven that the logarithmic approach is more accurate. Subsequently, based on the logarithmic displacement field, the variational approach yields the governing differential equations and boundary conditions of the EHSAPT. Finally, a numerical study is conducted for the non-linear response of a curved panel loaded by a distributed pressure at the upper face sheet. The non-linear study reveals that the post-buckling response of a curved sandwich panels is associated with deep or small wrinkling deformations of the upper face sheet in the case of a simply-supported panel or a general non-linear in the case of pinned supports.

1 INTRODUCTION

Analysis of flat sandwich panels, in general, may be described by two main categories. The first one assumes that the core is of anti-plane type, i.e. very stiff in the vertical directions (incompressible) and with negligible in-plane rigidity in the longitudinal direction (metallic honeycomb), see for example the textbooks [1-3]. Such panels may be modeled by computational models such as the First or High order sandwich panel models that replace the layered panel with an equivalent single layer, (ESL) and assume that the core is incompressible. The second approach is denoted as the layered approach and it is described through high-order models, see for example [4] that solved the core fields in a closed-form or [5] in which the displacement fields of the core are presumed. In such models the overall response is a combination of the responses of the face sheets and the core through equilibrium and compatibility.

Research on curved or shell sandwich panels includes ESL computational models that assume that the core is incompressible following the First-Order Shear Deformable (FOSD) Theory due to Reissner and Reissner- Mindlin. This approach has become the basis for a large number of research works for flat and curved panels respectively; Kollar [6] investigated the buckling of generally anisotropic shallow sandwich shells and Vaswani et al. [7] performed a vibration and damping analysis of curved sandwich beams. The last two models use the Flügge shell theory while assuming that the face sheets are membranes only and the core is incompressible. Shallow cylindrical sandwich panels with orthotropic surfaces adopting the FOSD models have been investigated by Ying-Jiang [8], but here the face sheet have membrane and flexural rigidities. Similarly, using the principle of virtual work along with the FOSD model and the Sanders non-linear stress-displacement relations, Di Sciuva [9] and Di Sciuva and Carrera [10] developed a model that takes into account the shear deformation but assumes that the core is incompressible and linear.

A class of high-order models based on the assumption of cubic and quadratic or trigonometric through-thickness distributions for the displacements have been suggested and summed by Librescu and Hause (2000) [11]. All the referenced high-order models use integration through the thickness along with variational principles and, in general, they are valid for sandwich panels with an incompressible core. The effect of the compressibility of the core using the HSAPT approach has been implemented in a number of research works on curved sandwich panels [12-15]. Recently, the effect of the in-plane core rigidity has been implemented in a series of papers through the use of the EHSAPT model, see for example Phan et al (2012) [16] for flat panels.

The mathematical formulation presented in this paper is based on the extended high-order sandwich panel theory (EHSAPT) to model the non-linear response of a curved sandwich panel. The sandwich panel is modeled as two curved faces, with membrane and flexural rigidities following the Euler-Bernoulli hypothesis, that are interconnected through compatibility and equilibrium with a 2-D compressible or extensible (i.e. compliant) elastic core with shear and radial (through-thickness) normal stress resistance. The EHSAPT model for the curved panel adopts the following assumptions: The face sheets have in-plane (circumferential) and bending rigidities with small moderate deformations class of kinematic relation [17-18] and negligible shear deformations; The core is considered as a 2D linear elastic continuum obeying small deformation kinematic relations and where the core height may change and the section plane does not remain plane after deformation; The core is assumed to possess shear, radial normal and circumferential stiffness; full bonding between the face sheets and the core is assumed and the interfacial layers can resist shear as well as radial normal stresses. Furthermore, the loads are applied to the face sheets only.

2 MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

The field equations and the boundary conditions are derived following the steps of the HSAPT approach for the curved sandwich panel, see Frostig [14] and Bozhevolnaya and Frostig [12]. The field equations are derived using the variational principle of extremum of the total potential energy as follows:

$$\delta(U + V) = 0$$

where U is in the internal potential strain energy and V is the external potential energy.

The internal potential energy in terms of polar coordinates of a fully bonded panel reads:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta U = & \int_0^\alpha \int_{-db/2}^{db/2} \int_{-1/2b_w}^{1/2b_w} \sigma_{sst}(\phi, z_t) \delta \varepsilon_{sst}(\phi, z_t) r_t dy dz_t d\phi + \\ & \int_0^\alpha \int_{-db/2}^{db/2} \int_{-1/2b_w}^{1/2b_w} \sigma_{ssb}(\phi, z_b) \delta \varepsilon_{ssb}(\phi, z_b) r_b dy dz_b d\phi + \\ & \int_0^\alpha \int_{r_{cb}}^{r_{ct}} \int_{-1/2b_w}^{1/2b_w} \left(\tau_c(\phi, r_c) \delta \gamma_c(\phi, r_c) + \sigma_{rrc}(\phi, r_c) \delta \varepsilon_{rrc}(\phi, r_c) + \right. \\ & \left. \sigma_{ssc}(\phi, r_c) \delta \varepsilon_{ssc}(\phi, r_c) \right) r_c dy dr_c d\phi \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $\sigma_{ssj}(\phi, r_j)$ and $\varepsilon_{ssj}(\phi, r_j)$ ($j=t, b$) are the normal in-plane and the shear stresses and strains of the face sheets, respectively; $\tau_{rs}(\phi, r_c)$ and $\gamma_{rs}(\phi, r_c)$ are the shear stresses and strains, respectively; $\sigma_{rr}(\phi, r_c)$ and $\varepsilon_{rr}(\phi, r_c)$ are the radial normal stresses and strains, respectively; $\sigma_{ss}(\phi, r_c)$ and $\varepsilon_{ss}(\phi, r_c)$ are the circumferential normal stresses and strains, respectively; r and s refer to the circumferential and radial directions of the curved panel; α is the angle of the curved panel; r_j ($j=t, b, c$) are the radii of the centroidal lines of the face sheets and the core, respectively; r_{cj} ($j=t, b$) refers to the radii of the upper and the lower interface line, respectively, where $r_{ct}=r_t-d/2$ and $r_{cb}=r_b+d_b/2$; and b_w and d_j ($j=t, b$) are the width and the thicknesses of the face sheets, respectively, and δ is the variational operator. For geometry, sign conventions, coordinates, deformations and internal resultants, see Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Dimensions, signs conventions and loads of a curved sandwich panel:
(a) geometry; (b) loads applied at face sheets.

The variation of the external energy reads:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \delta V = & -\int_0^\alpha (n_t \delta u_{ot}(\phi) + q_t \delta w_t(\phi)) r_t d\phi - \int_0^\alpha (n_b \delta u_{ob}(\phi) + q_b \delta w_b(\phi)) r_b d\phi - \\
 & \sum_{\phi_e=0}^\alpha N_{et}(\phi_e) \delta u_{ot}(\phi_e) - P_{et}(\phi_e) \delta w_t(\phi_e) + M_{et}(\phi_e) \delta \beta_t(\phi_e) - N_{eb}(\phi_e) \delta u_{ob}(\phi_e) - \\
 & P_{eb}(\phi_e) \delta w_b(\phi_e) + M_{eb}(\phi_e) \delta \beta_b(\phi_e)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where

$$\beta_j(\phi_e) = \frac{u_{oj}(\phi_e) - D(w_j)(\phi_e)}{r_j}$$

where n_j , q_j and m_j ($j=t,b$) are the external distributed loads in the circumferential and radial directions, respectively, and the distributed bending moment applied at the face sheets; u_{oj} and w_j ($j=t,b$) are the circumferential and radial displacements of the face sheets, respectively; β_j is the slope of the section of the face sheet; N_{ej} , P_{ej} and M_{ej} ($j=t,b$) are the external loads in the circumferential and radial directions, respectively, and the bending moment applied at the edges ($\phi_e=0,\alpha$) of the various face sheets. For sign conventions and definition of loads see Fig. 1.

The displacements pattern of the face sheets through their depth follows the Euler-Bernoulli assumptions with negligible shear strain and kinematic relations of small deformation and they read, ($j=t,b$):

$$u_j(\phi, z_j) = u_{oj}(\phi) + \beta_j z_j \quad \text{where} \quad \beta_j = (u_{oj}(\phi) - \frac{d}{d\phi} w_j(\phi)) / r_j \tag{3}$$

and $u_{oj}(\phi)$ and $\beta_j(\phi)$ are the in-plane displacements of the centroid of the face sheets section and its rotation respectively; z_j is the radial coordinate measured *upward* from the centroid of each face sheet, r_j is the radius and ϕ is the angle measured from origin, see Fig. 1 for geometry. Hence, the strain distributions reads ($j=t,b$):

$$\varepsilon_{ssj}(\phi) = \varepsilon_{ossj}(\phi) + \chi_j(\phi) z_j, \gamma_{srj}(\phi) = \psi_j(\phi) - \frac{u_{oj}(\phi) - \frac{d}{d\phi} w_j(\phi)}{r_j} \tag{4}$$

where the mid-plane strain includes a non-linear term and the curvature equal:

$$\varepsilon_{ss,oj} = \frac{\frac{d}{d\phi} u_{oj}(\phi) + w_j(\phi)}{r_j} + 1/2 \beta_j^2, \chi_j(\phi) = \frac{\frac{d}{d\phi} \beta_j(\phi)}{r_j} \tag{5}$$

The kinematic relations for the core adopting the approximation of small deformations read:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \varepsilon_{ss}(\phi, r_c) &= \frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} u_c(\phi, r_c) + w_c(\phi, r_c)}{r_c}, \varepsilon_{rrc}(\phi, r_c) = \frac{\partial}{\partial r_c} w_c(\phi, r_c) \\
 \gamma_{rs}(\phi, r_c) &= \frac{\partial}{\partial r_c} u_c(\phi, r_c) - \frac{u_c(\phi, r_c)}{r_c} + \frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} w_c(\phi, r_c)}{r_c}
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

where the displacements distributions read:

$$u_c(\phi, r_c) = u_o(\phi) + u_1(\phi)r_c + \frac{u_2(\phi)}{r_c} + u_3(\phi)\ln\left(\frac{r_c}{r_{ce}}\right)$$

$$w_c(\phi, r_c) = w_o(\phi) + \frac{w_1(\phi)}{r_c} + w_2(\phi)\ln\left(\frac{r_c}{r_{ce}}\right)$$

where $w_c(\phi, r)$ and $u_c(\phi, r)$ are the radial and the circumferential displacement of the core, respectively and r_{ce} is the radius of the centroid of the core section. These distributions take the form of the core displacement fields that have been closed-form solved for the curved HSAPT model, see Frostig (1999).

The compatibility conditions corresponding to perfect bonding between the face sheets and the core require that:

$$u_c(\phi, r = r_{jc}) = u_{oj}(\phi) + (-1)^k \frac{d_j}{2} \beta_j(\phi) \quad (7)$$

$$w_c(\phi, r = r_{jc}) = w_j(\phi)$$

where $k=1$ when $j=t$ and 0 when $j=b$ and r_{cj} ($j=t, b$) are the radii of the upper and the lower face-core interfaces, respectively, $u_c(r=r_{cj}, \phi)$ and $w_c(r=r_{cj}, \phi)$ are the displacements of the core, in the circumferential and the radial directions at the face-core interfaces. Actually, Eqs. (7) describes four conditions denoted by com_{ju} (first equation) and com_{jw} (second equations) ($j=t, b$) for the upper and the lower face-core interfaces respectively. The compatibility equations are implemented in the formulation through Lagrange multipliers as follows:

$$\delta U_\lambda = \int_0^\alpha (\lambda_{tu}(\phi) \delta com_{tu}(\phi) r_{ct} + \lambda_{bu}(\phi) \delta com_{bu}(\phi) r_{cb} + \lambda_{tw}(\phi) \delta com_{tw}(\phi) r_{ct} + \lambda_{bw}(\phi) \delta com_{bw}(\phi) r_{cb} + \delta \lambda_{tu} com_{tu}(\phi) r_{ct} + \delta \lambda_{bu} com_{bu}(\phi) r_{cb} + \delta \lambda_{tw} com_{tw}(\phi) r_{ct} + \delta \lambda_{bw} com_{bw}(\phi) r_{cb}) d\phi \quad (8)$$

where λ_{ju} and λ_{jw} ($j=t, b$) are the Lagrange multipliers in the circumferential and radial directions at the upper and the lower face-core interfaces respectively.

The field equations and the boundary conditions are derived using the variational principle; the variational expression of the energies, see Eqs. (1) and (2); the kinematic relations of the face sheets and the core, Eqs. (4) to (6), the compatibility requirements, see Eqs. (7), and the stress resultants along with high-order ones. The field equations are derived after integration by parts and some algebraic manipulations.

3 NUMERICAL STUDY

The numerical part presents the non-linear response of a simply-supported curved panel when subjected to a distributed pressure load. The non-linear response uses a loading control

scheme for the load changes and it starts with low loads that yield a linear response and reaches high loads that are deep in the non-linear regime. The sandwich panel consists of two aluminum face sheets of a thickness of 1mm and an H160 foam core made by Devinicell with $E_{cs} = E_{cr} = E_c = 170$ MPa and $G_c = 66$ MPa with a thickness of 25 mm and a Poisson ratio of 0.3. The geometry of the curved panel is that of an experimental set-up, see [12-13]. Two schemes of boundary conditions are considered: A simply-supported panel where all edges of the face sheets and the core are supported by radial rollers except for the left edge of the upper face sheet that is restrained to circumferential movements; and the second scheme consists of pinned supports at edges of all constituents.

Figure 2: Deformed shapes of a uniformly loaded simply-supported (rollers) long curved panel: (a) panel layout; (b) deformed shapes.

For the Simply-Supported case, two panels have been considered a long span of 500.0 mm and a short one of 250.0 mm with a constant radius. The response in general is similar – in both cases it is associated with wrinkling waves at the upper face sheets, but with different quantities as well as for some structural variables the response is quite different. Fig. 2 shows

the deformed shapes at various load levels; it reveals smooth curves, in the upper face sheet, for low load levels and in the post buckling (non-linear) range, in the form of non-regular shallow dimples within the central part of the panel. Please notice that wrinkling appears only at the upper face sheet while the curves of the lower face sheet are smooth through the loading sequence.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The paper presents the response of a curved sandwich panels, within the framework of the EHSAPT model, i.e. where with the circumferential rigidity of the core is considered. The mathematical formulation presumes that the displacements through the thickness of the core follows the functional pattern that have been derived in the closed-form solution of the HSAPT model of the curved sandwich panel. In general, it is a sum of a number of terms that take an explicit description in the radial direction and unknown functions in the circumferential direction. The formulation uses the non-linear and linear kinematic relations, for the face sheets and the core respectively, along with a variational principle to derive the non-linear field equations for the face sheets and the core. As a result of the presumed distribution, the formulation involves ordinary stress resultants for the face sheets and the core as well as high-order (non-polynomial) stress resultants for the core. The formulation uses Lagrange multipliers to enforce compatibility in the radial and hoop directions at the face-core interfaces and finally yields a set of 9 ordinary differential equations.

The numerical study investigates the non-linear response of some sandwich panel configurations; two types of boundary conditions have been considered. In order to validate the model, a comparison with a linear elasticity closed-form solution has been conducted and the results show very good agreement.

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